

Preparation and Properties of Highly Concentrated Sols.

Part V. Stannic Hydroxide Sols.

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In previous publications (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 315, 441, 455; *Kolloid Z.*, 1935, 71, 173) from these laboratories we have reported the preparation and properties of highly concentrated sols of aluminium, iron, chromium, zirconium, and thorium hydroxides, vanadium pentoxide and silicic and molybdic acids. In the present paper, we are communicating our results on highly concentrated stannic hydroxide sols.

Preparation of the Sol.

Stannic chloride (hydrated crystals 45 g.) was dissolved in 100 c.c. of water and very strong ammonium hydroxide was gradually added with constant stirring. Heat is evolved in the reaction and therefore the beaker was kept in a cold water-bath. When a sufficient quantity of ammonium hydroxide had been added, a viscous gel was obtained. It was repeatedly washed with distilled water, and then it was peptised with a minimum quantity of strong ammonium hydroxide. The sample, washed 14 times with water, took about 4 hours to give a clear sol.

The sol thus prepared was further concentrated by slow evaporation. At a certain stage a scum appeared on the surface, and on further concentration, a jelly was formed. The sol at this stage, before the formation of the jelly contained 68.4 g. SnO_2 per litre. The sols of the following concentrations were obtained :

	Prepared in the cold.	Concentrated by evaporation.
Sol I	65.4 g. /litre	68.4 g. /litre
Sol II. (purer)	45.0	80.9

These sols on dialysis for about two days form transparent jellies in the dialyser. A sol obtained by washing the gel for three days contained as much as 90.2 g. of SnO_2 per litre. This sol was also

converted into a jelly when left exposed to atmosphere. The concentrations of the sol prepared over sulphuric acid in a desiccator also gave 89.8 g. SnO₂ per litre.

Coagulations of the Sol.

It was difficult to study the coagulation of very highly concentrated sols by the addition of electrolytes. The coagulation of the following sols has been studied.

TABLE I.

Amount of sol taken = 0.5 c.c. Total volume = 15 c.c. Time of observation = 1 hour.

Days dialysed.	Electrolyte.	Ppt. conc.	Conc. of the sol in SnO ₂ /litre.
4	KCl	0.07330	40.6 g.
	BaCl ₂	0.00052	
	Al(NO ₃) ₃	0.0004	
5	KCl	0.06	40.2
	BaCl ₂	0.00038	
	Al(NO ₃) ₃	0.00028	
7	KCl	0.0269	41.2
	BaCl ₂	0.00024	
	Al(NO ₃) ₃	0.00018	
10	KCl	0.01133	41.4
	BaCl ₂	0.00016	
	Al(NO ₃) ₃	0.00014	

The precipitating ratios are given in the following table. The value from the trivalent ion has been taken as unity.

TABLE II.

	The sols dialysed for			
	2 days.	5 days.	7 days.	10 days.
Monovalent	183.4	169.2	145.2	78.6
Bivalent	1.302	1.364	1.296	1.11
Trivalent	1.00	1.0	1.00	1.00

It will be seen from these figures that the sols, which have been dialysed for a longer time, require smaller amounts of electrolyte for coagulation. Moreover, the ratio of the precipitating concentrations of mono, bi and trivalent ions decreases continuously as the dialysis proceeds, that is, as the purity of the sol increases. Similar results were obtained by Dhar and collaborators on other highly concentrated sols, and as the purity increases, the precipitation concentrations approach the ratios required by the expression of Chakravarti, Ghosh and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 330).

$$N_1 : N_2 : N_3 = 1 : \frac{1}{2}\alpha : \frac{1}{3}\alpha^2 : \dots$$

$$\text{Where } \alpha = e^{\frac{-q\epsilon/DR}{kT}}$$

It may also be noted here, that the coagulum obtained from an impure sol is opalescent, whereas that from a pure sol is transparent.

Purity of the Sol.

The concentrated sols of stannic hydroxide contain traces of chloride ions, and a sufficient amount of ammonium hydroxide as impurity, as shown from the following table. Ammonia was estimated colourimetrically by Nessler's reagent, and chloride gravimetrically as AgCl.

TABLE III.

Days dialysed	Conc. of SnO ₂ per litre.	Cl ⁻ ion per litre.	Conc. of ammonia.
2	40.6 g.	0.5494 g.	0.1105 N
5	40.2	0.0301	0.0458
7	41.2	Traces	0.0371
10	42.4	„	0.0236

Viscosity of Sols.

It was reported in previous publications, that the highly concentrated sols of iron, chromium, aluminium, thorium and zirconium hydroxides possess a very high viscosity, and also that the viscosity markedly increases with the purity of the sols. However, the stannic hydroxide sols do not show very high viscosity even on dialysis.

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With continued dialysis, the concentration of the sol falls markedly. Some of the results are given in the following table.

TABLE IV.

Temperature = 30°. Viscosity of water at 30° = 0.010023.

Days of dialysis.	Density.	Conc. of SnO ₂ per litre.	Viscosity.
Undialysed sol.	1.1026	90.4 g.	0.01018
1	1.084	85.4	0.01018
1	1.076	76.6	0.01193
3	1.069	69.7	0.01245
3	1.059	59.0	0.01294
7	1.047	50.2	0.01218
9	1.042	40.4	0.01213

It has been observed that even a very pure sol, which sets to a jelly on standing, does not possess a high viscosity as was observed with other concentrated sols. The ageing effect of the sol on the viscosity of undialysed and dialysed sols is also not marked, except in those cases where the sol sets to a gel on standing for some days.

Jelly Formation with Stannic Hydroxide.

Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1922, 26, 681) has studied the jelly formation of stannic hydroxide. The concentrated sols which we have obtained give a transparent jelly when treated with hydrochloric acid, potassium and barium chlorides. Some of the jellies are markedly thixotropic and are converted to sols when shaken, but again set to jellies on standing. Some of the results are given in Table V.

TABLE V.

Concentration of the sol dialysed for 19 days = 37.2 g. of SnO_2 /litre. Amounts of the sol taken = 4 c.c. Total volume = 5 c.c.

Concentration of KCl(M)	0.003105	0.003726	0.004347	0.004968	0.005589	0.006210
Time of gelation in minutes.	175	72	2.3	10	5	2
Thixotropic time in minutes for re-setting.	5	8	1	...	...	...

Electric Conductivity of the Sols.

We have also studied the electric conductivities of stannic hydroxide sols dialysed for a different number of days, and also the influence of dilution and temperature on conductivity of a particular sol. The results are given below :

TABLE VI.

Temperature = 35°.

Days of dialysis.	Concentration of SnO_2 /litre.	Sp. conductivity in mhos $\times 10^{-4}$.	Days of dialysis.	Concentration of SnO_2 /litre.	Sp. conductivity in mhos $\times 10^{-4}$.
1	85.4 g.	29.85	5	29.5	6.13
"	47.7	15.83	7	50.2	9.14
"	76.6	20.12	"	25.1	4.81
"	38.3	12.86	9	41.4	7.55
3	69.7	16.46	"	21.2	3.72
"	34.8	8.33	11	37.7	6.56
5	59.0	14.06	"	18.8	2.66

TABLE VII.

Temperature = 35°.

Dilution.	Sp. conductivity in mhos $\times 10^{-4}$.	Sp. conductivity $\times 10^{-4}$ as calculated.
90.2 g./litre (A)	50.05	50.05
A/2	30.69	61.38
A/4	19.49	77.96
A/8	11.62	90.82
A/16	6.66	109.8
A/32	5.47	173.3

TABLE VIII.

Concentration of the two days' dialysed sol = 82.2 g. of SnO_2 /litre.

Temp.	Sp. conductivity $\times 10^{-4}$.
25°	19.09
35°	22.96
45°	26.03

From these results, it will be seen that on dialysis, as the purity increases, the conductivity of the sol decreases. The influence of temperature on the conductivity is also regular. The results in the Table VII show that the conductivity multiplied by the dilution of the sol goes on increasing as the dilution proceeds.

An attempt was also made to study the cataphoresis of the stannic hydroxide particles by the improved method of Mukherjee, but the difficulty was in procuring a sharp boundary in a non-opalescent colourless sol of stannic hydroxide. Various indicators, as phenolphthalein and methylene blue were tried. No indicator was necessary for the undialysed sol which was sufficiently opalescent to give a sharp boundary. The results are given in Table IX. The cataphoretic movement was extremely slow.

TABLE IX.

Voltage applied = 170. Time = 30 min.

Days dialysed.	Conc. of SnO ₂ /litre.	Conc. of KCl as the upper liquid.	Movement of	
			Left limb.	Right limb.
undialysed	40.5 g.	N/5	3 mm.	3 mm.
			Voltage reversed	
	"	"	3 mm.	3 mm.
1 day	37.3	N/16	3 mm.	4 mm.
			Voltage reversed	
	"	"	4 mm.	3 mm.

SUMMARY.

1. A highly concentrated sol of negatively charged stannic hydroxide has been prepared of a concentration of 98.4 grams SnO₂ per litre by peptising well washed stannic hydroxide with concentrated ammonia, and evaporating the sol on a water-bath. An attempt to further concentrate it, resulted in the formation of a jelly.

2. The coagulation of concentrated sols has been studied, and it was found that as the purity increases on dialysis, the ratio of precipitating concentrations of mono, bi and trivalent ions goes on decreasing.

3. The stannic hydroxide sols do not possess so high viscosities as iron, chromium and thorium hydroxides. The electric conductivities have also been studied.

4. The colloidal particles of stannic hydroxide show a very slow cataphoretic movement.

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